

FINANCIAL OPENNESS, FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

OKOIARIKPO BENJAMIN OKOI

*Department of Economics, University of Calabar, Calabar
Email: okoibenokoi@gmail.com, Phone number: 07031147069*

KENNETH CHUKWUMA CHECHE

*Department of Economics, University of Calabar, Calabar
Email: kennethcheche@gmail.com, Phone number: 08036000744*

MOSES ULOMA ANYANWU

*Port Harcourt Electricity Distribution Company (PHED), Calabar
Email: anyanwumoses10@gmail.com, Phone number: 08075084950*

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of financial openness and financial development on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries during the period 1996 to 2024 by using a sample of 39 countries. Employing the Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) estimator with robust standard errors, the study found that financial openness has a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth in SSA, while the effect of financial development is positive but insignificant. The study also found that institutional quality, measured as the index of government effectiveness, has positive and significant economic growth effects in SSA. Based on the results derived, the study recommended that the governments of SSA countries implement measures to address the challenges to the effective utilization of financial services in the region such as infrastructural deficits and financial literacy. The study also recommended that efforts should be made towards improving the quality of government institutions with a view to increasing the effectiveness of government.

Keywords: Financial openness, financial development, economic growth, Sub-Saharan Africa.

JEL Codes: C23, F43, G18, G44 and O40.

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial openness and financial development are theoretically regarded as key economic growth drivers. This is due to the financial sector's performance of productivity enhancing functions, which as identified by the World Bank Group (2026) include the production of information on potential investments and allocation of capital, overseeing investments and exertion of corporate governance after fiancé has been provided, facilitation of the diversification, trade and management of risks, mobilize and pool savings and, easing the exchange of services and goods. On the other hand, financial openness can foster economic growth in several ways. The first of this is through its role in promoting the transfer of managerial skills, technology and other knowledge from foreign sources. Furthermore, financial openness, by encouraging the entry by foreign firms into the domestic economy, also increases its competitiveness (Estrada et al., 2015). This theoretical establishment of the link between these variables has resulted in the drive towards rapid financial sector development and financial openness by countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). This has been based on the use of measures such as the establishment of institutions such as deposit insurance institutions including the Kenya Deposit Insurance Corporation, Asset

Management Corporation of Nigeria, Ghana Deposit Protection Corporation, Zimbabwe Asset Management Corporation. Microfinance institutions have also been established to drive financial inclusion in the region, while legislative frameworks and policies targeted at the development of digital-mobile banking systems, such as the M-Pesa introduced in Kenya and, O-Pay and Money Point in Nigeria, have been introduced. Furthermore, SSA countries have liberalized their capital accounts with a view to increasing the level of financial openness of their economies.

However, despite its potential to contribute positively to economic growth, recent studies, as highlighted by Carneiro et al (2016), have shown that excessive financial development can negatively impact an economy. Carneiro et al (2016) observe that this could be due to increased volatility as a result of the increased likelihood of booms and busts due to excessive access to finance, excessive finance induced diversion of human capital and talent away from productive sectors towards the financial sector, and financial and economic volatility due to excessive risk taking and leveraging. Again, foreign capital inflows, associated with financial openness might be misallocated in the absence of efficient and strong financial systems and thus precipitate growth-constraining financial crisis (Estrada et al., 2015).

Overall, SSA's performance with respect to financial sector performance has been mixed. This is reflected in data on the financial depth measured as growth rates of broad money to gross domestic product (GDP) and domestic credit to the private sector to GDP as published by the World Bank (2026a) and World Bank (2026b). For instance, computations of the 30-year average ratio of broad money to GDP measure of financial depth, based on data from the World Bank (2026a), yields a value of 53.17%, relative to the global 30-year average of 127.67%, indicating improving but relatively low levels of financial access and financial intermediation. This is buttressed by computations of the 30-year average ratio of domestic credit to the private sector to GDP measure of financial depth, based on data from the World Bank (2026b), yields a value of 44.056%, relative to the global average of 110.79%.

SSA is also characterized by a moderately low degree of financial openness. This is reflected in the 30-year average Chin and Ito KAOPEN index measure of financial openness of -0.4849, computed using data from the Chin and Ito (2023). This implies that the region was characterized by a significant amount of capital account controls and restrictions on the flow of certain types of capital during the period.

Given SSA region's need for high and sustained rates of economic growth, its mixed performance of SSA with respect to the indices of financial development and openness emphasizes the need for the assessment of the efforts made in the region with respect to the openness and development of its financial sector. The pertinence of such an assessment is informed by the sub-regions equally mixed growth performance during the period 1996 to 2024. This can be seen in data from the World Bank (2026c) which reveals a decline in economic growth in SSA, measured as the growth rate of gross domestic product, from 5.16% in 1996 to 2.17% in 1999, with an increase to 6.39% in 2002 during the second year of the current century, and a decline to 4.12% in 2004, but increasing again to 6.15% in 2007.

The data from the World Bank (2026c) further reveals that economic growth in SSA decreased to 3.14% in 2009 in the aftermath of the Great Recession in the global economy, but decreased to 3.33% in 2012. In 2013, economic growth in SSA increased to 5.12%. It however declined to 1.23% in 2016 during the final year of the Ebola pandemic. Since 2017, economic growth in SSA while fluctuating has been below 5%, with a negative growth rate of -3.23% during the height of

the COVID-19 pandemic. Given the mixed performance of SSA with respect to both financial openness and development, and economic growth, this study attempts to achieve two objectives: examine the effect of financial openness on economic growth SSA and; investigate the effect of the questions that arise with respect to the relationship between the variables by investigating the financial development on economic growth in SSA. The study is structured into five sections: introduction, literature review, methodology, results and discussion of findings and, conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Financial development and economic growth

The results of recent empirical literature on the growth effects of financial development in SSA have yielded mixed results depending on the approach to measurement of financial development. The latter literature includes the study carried out by Shobande (2017) which examined the effect of the development of the stock market and deposit money banks on economic growth in Nigeria in the long-term by using the Error Correction Model and data for the years 1980 to 2016. The study found that stock market development, measured as market capitalization ratio, has a negative and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria in the long-run, while the effect of deposit money banks, measured as banking sector development, is positive and significant.

Another study by Yusheng et al. (2020) examined the impact of financial development on economic growth in 32 countries in SSA through the use of dynamic panel data analysis techniques. The study found that financial development indicators such as bank credit to the private sector has mixed but more significant effect on economic growth in the SSA than broad money and liquid liabilities as measures of financial development. On the other hand, financial development measured as a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based index of financial development and, the simultaneous occurrence of financial development and human capital development-computed through the interaction of financial development and human capital development variables- have positive effects on economic growth in SSA.

A similar study by Machado et al. (2021) utilized the SGMM estimator and data for the years 1980 to 2015 to examine the relationship between financial development and economic growth in 36 countries in SSA. From the results of the study revealed the existence of a U-shaped relationship between financial development and economic growth in SSA. Specifically, the results show that financial development measured as the ratio of liquid liabilities to GDP is harmful to economic growth in SSA after the threshold of 11.8%, while domestic credit to the private sector to GDP measure of financial development is harmful to economic growth after the 6.9% threshold.

Ikubor et al. (2022) which utilized the Ordinary Least Squares and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ADL) model and data for the years 1981 to 2021 in examining the economic growth effects of financial development in Nigeria, found that financial development, measured as interest rate, ratio of broad money to GDP, total bank credit, total bank liabilities have significant effects on economic growth in Nigeria. The study further found that financial development measured as the ratio private sector credit to GDP had an insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Another study by Hyacinth et al. (2023) which utilized the Generalized Least Squares estimator and data for the years 1995 to 2022 found that financial development measured as the market sector index has a negative but significant effect on economic growth, measured as GDP per-capita, in SSA, while the effect of financial development measured as the banking sector index is positive and significant.

On the other hand, the study by Ibrahim and Alagidede (2018) utilized the System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) estimator and data on 29 Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries covering the period 1980 to 2014 in investigating the impact of financial development on economic growth in SSA. From the GMM estimates, the study found that financial development is growth supporting in SSA.

Jibir et al. (2023) examined the impact of financial development on innovation-led economic growth in 30 SSA countries between 2001 and 2018 through the use of the systemic panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model. The results of the study revealed that financial development, measured as the ratio of private credit to GDP, has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in the long-run. The study also found that innovation, measured as the citation index of scientific and technical journal articles, has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in SSA in the long-run and an insignificant effect in the short-run.

A related study Dan`Asabe and Mustapha (2023) evaluated the effect of the development of financial development and trade openness on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2019 through the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The study found that financial development, measured as the ratio of broad money supply to GDP, has a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria in the long-run, while the effect of trade openness is positive and significant. The study also found that trade openness has an insignificant effect on economic growth in the short-run, while the effect of the two-year lag of financial development is positive and significant.

Another study by Fengju and Wubishet (2024) investigated the effects of financial development on economic growth in 18 countries in East Africa (EA) while accounting for the effects of institutional quality. The study which used the panel System Generalized Method of Moments estimator and data spanning the years 1995 to 2021 found that while financial development has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in the economies of EA, such effect is amplified in countries characterized by stronger institutional frameworks.

Financial deepening, used as a measure of financial development, was found to have significant positive effects on economic growth in Nigeria in both long and short-run time periods by the study carried out by Nuhu and Ima`il (2024), which also utilized ARDL model and data for the period 1980 to 2022. Finally, Enemona et al. (2024) utilized the Mean Group estimator and data on 27 African countries for the period 2005 to 2022, in examining the effect of financial development on the achievement of inclusive growth in Africa found that financial development has a significant effect on the attainment on inclusive growth in Africa.

2.2 Financial openness and economic growth

Overall, while a significant amount of empirical literature exists on the growth effects of financial development in SSA and other countries, a significant gap still exists in empirical literature on the effects of financial openness on economic growth, globally. One recent study by Liu et al. (2026) used the fixed effects (FE), and two-stage least squares (2SLS) panel data estimators and data for the period 1980 and 2022 to examine the effect of the openness of the capital account on economic growth in emerging market economies. The results of both FE and 2SLE estimation revealed that capital account openness, measured as the Chinn-Itto KAOPEN index, has a positive and significant effect on economic growth, measured as GDP per capita, in the emerging market

economies. In particular, the results indicated the existence of an inverted U-shaped relationship between both variables in the economies.

Finally, Seti et al. (2025) employed the generalized method of moments estimator and data for the period 1970 to 2023 in investigating the effect of financial openness and trade openness on economic growth in ten developing and emerging countries including Nigeria, China, India, South Africa, Brazil, Kenya, Russia, Mexico, Vietnam and Indonesia. The study found that financial openness, measured using the Chinn–Ito KAOPEN index, and trade openness, have a positive and significant effect on economic growth in the ten countries.

Overall, the review of empirical literature on the growth effects of financial development and financial openness on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa which revealing the existence of mixed results on such effects, also indicates that such existing studies have mainly utilized methods such as the panel generalized methods of moments, panel autoregressive distributed lag model and panel structural vector autoregressive. This study attempts to provide evidence of the relationship between the variables through the use of Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) based approach, based on the relevant robustness tests.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this study is Paul Romer’s endogenous growth theory. In Romer’s model, technological change, which drives economic growth, is endogenous in nature because it depends on capital accumulation and population growth. The theory links the development of new ideas which drives technological change to the number of persons employed in the knowledge sector-the effort geared towards research and development-in an economy. Such new ideas are regarded as the main driver of productivity in an economy. Overall, the theory predicts that the growth rate of an economy will increase as the share of persons employed in the knowledge sector, or population increases (Morley, 2015). The model developed by Paul Romer is based on a production function specified as follows:

$$Q = f(AK^{\alpha}L^{\beta}) \tag{1}$$

Where: Q = Output, A = Technology, K = Capital, L = Labor, and α and β = Returns to scale

The use of Romer’s endogenous growth theory as the theoretical anchor for this study is informed by Romer’s identification of the spillovers of the outcome of investment in research and development by firms in an economy which lead to the accumulation of the “knowledge” component of capital stock as the primary-endogenous- driver of productivity and hence economic growth in an economy. However, firms’ investment in research and development is in its self a function of several factors among which are its access to finance which is in turn is dependent on the level of development of the financial system and degree of financial openness of the economy.

3.2 Model specification

The model for this study is specified in functional form on the basis of Romer’s endogenous growth theory as adapted for the study. The model is presented as follows:

$$\log RGDP = \delta_{0it} + \delta_{1it}FDIN_{it} + \delta_{2it}FPEN_{it} + \delta_{3it}LBOR_{it} + \delta_{4it}\log EXCE_{it} + \delta_{5it}GEOF_{it} + \delta_{6it}RULA_{it} + U_{it} \tag{2}$$

Where: $RGDP_{it}$ = Real gross domestic product of the i^{th} country in time t , $FDIN_{it}$ = Financial sector development in the i^{th} country in time t (measured using the Financial Development Index developed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF)), $FPEN_{it}$ = Financial openness in the i^{th} country in time t (measured using the Chin and Ito (2023) KAOPEN index which has also been utilized by Estrade et al. (2015), Seti et al. (2025) and Liu et al. (2026)), $LBOR_{it}$ = Labor force in the i^{th} country in time t , $GOEF_{it}$ = Index of government effectiveness in the i^{th} country in time t (used as a measure of institutional quality), $RULA_{it}$ = Index of rule of law in the i^{th} country in time t (used as a measure of institutional quality), and $EXCE_{it}$ = Exchange rate in the i^{th} country in time t , and U_{it} = Stochastic error term.

Equation (2) is estimated using the Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) panel data estimator with robust standard errors. The study also employs descriptive statistics, Pesaran test for cross-sectional independence, Pesaran-Yamagata (2008) Delta Test for Slope Homogeneity, Cross-Sectionally Augmented IM–Pesaran–Shin panel unit root test, and Westerlund test for cointegration, while the Augmented Mean Group (AMG) Estimator with robust standard errors is used as a robustness test.

The study utilizes panel data, with its time series component covering the period 1996 to 2024. The cross-sectional unit component of the panel (SSA countries) is determined using the Taro-Yamane approach to sample size determination as follows: $n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$, where: n = Sample size, N = Population size and e = Level of precision. SSA is comprised of 49 countries. Based on this, the sample size, and thus number of cross-sectional unites included in the panel is determined as follows: $n = \frac{49}{1+49(0.0025)} = 43.652561247 \approx 44$ countries. However, due to issues with respect to the availability of data on some SSA countries and the need to ensure accuracy with respect to data on the variables, the sample size for the study is reduced to 39 countries.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first result presented in this section is the descriptive statistics on the variables included in the study model. The descriptive statistics which are contained in table 1 show that the average growth rate of the economies of the 39 countries that make up the sample size for this study was significantly high during the period 1996 to 2024. The standard deviation indicates a significant level of heterogeneity among in economic growth rate among the countries.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
lrgdp	1,131	22.17346	3.439231	6.984289	27.03436
fdin	1,131	0.143811	0.107475	0.003837	0.592519
fpen	1,131	-0.48495	1.372045	-1.93109	2.3
lexce	1,131	4.790511	2.147606	-1.81065	9.165874
lbor	1,131	66.2013	15.17678	16.47	90.305
goef	1,131	-0.6758	0.599466	-1.88091	1.15004
rula	1,131	-0.75374	0.642984	-2.59088	1.04419

Source: Authors` (2026).

The mean values of the levels of financial development and openness, and the labor force and exchange rate among the SSA countries included in the study are significantly small, with the negative mean value of financial openness indicating that on the average, most economies in SSA

were less financially open during the period covered by the study indicating, while the positive mean value of financial development indicates a low level of financial development among the countries during the period. The mean value of the exchange rate indicates a significant level exchange rate depreciation among the countries during the period covered by the study.

The stand deviation values of the level of financial openness indicates the existence of significant difference among the SSA countries included in the study with respect to the openness of their financial sectors, while the relatively small size of the standard deviation of the level of financial development indicates the existence of moderate differences among the countries with respect to the development of their respective financial sectors. This is also true of the standard deviations of the exchange rates and labor force of the countries which indicate significant differences among them with respect to these variables, particularly with respect to the labor force which indicates a high level of heterogeneity of the labor force among the SSA countries included in the study.

On the other hand, the mean values of the indexes of government effectiveness and rule of law are small and negative, indicating that on the average the governments in the SSA countries included in the study have been ineffective and the rule of law not enforced. The standard deviation values of both variables indicate the existence of moderate differences between the countries selected in the study with respect to government effectiveness and rule of law.

After presenting the results of the descriptive statistics, the next result presented is the result of the test for cross-sectional independence and slope heterogeneity. The results of the test of cross-sectional independence, carried out through the use of Pesaran’s test and presented in table 2, indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence, implying the existence of strong cross-sectional dependence among the SSA countries included in the panel, meaning that the SSA countries included in the study are vulnerable to spillover effects and unobserved shocks. The consequence of this is that the t-statistics will be overstated, and the estimates biased and spurious.

Table 2: Pesaran Test for Cross Sectional Dependence

Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence	45.750
Pr	0.0000

Source: Authors` (2026).

The result of the second test, the Pesaran and Yamagata test for slope heterogeneity, presented in table 3 indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis of slope homogeneity in the panel data. This is because the probability values of both Delta and Adjusted Delta statistics are less than the 5% level of significance based critical value of 0.05.

Table 3: Pesaran-Yamagata (2008) Test for Slope Homogeneity in Panels

H0: slope coefficients are homogenous		
	Delta	p-value
	22.894	0.000
adj.	26.904	0.000

Source: Authors` (2026).

Based on the results of the test for cross-sectional independence and slope homogeneity, the study employs second generation panel approaches to the analysis of data on the relevant variables. The first of such tests is the Pesaran cross-sectionally augmented Dickey-Fuller (CADF) unit root test. The result of this test, presented in table 4, indicates that the variables included in the study model, are of mixed order of integration.

Table 4: Pesaran Cross-Sectionally Augmented Dickey-Fuller (CADF) Unit Root Test

Variable	At Levels		At First Difference		Order of Integration
	CIPS Statistic	5% Critical Value	CIPS Statistic	5% Critical Value	
lrgdp	-2.171	-2.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)
fdin	-3.367	-2.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)
fpen	-1.557	-2.11	-2.419	-2.11	<i>I</i> (1)
lexce	-3.006	-2.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)
lbor	-2.604	-2.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)
goef	-2.937	-2.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)
rula	-2.358	-1.11	-	-	<i>I</i> (0)

Source: Authors` (2026).

Table 5: Westerlund Cointegration Test

	Statistic	p-value
Variance ratio	6.7607	0.000

Source: Author`s computation (2026).

The variables included in the study model are also tested for cointegration through the use of Westerlund’s test. The result of this test, presented in table 5, indicates that the variable is cointegrated. Based on this, and the results of the unit root, the study employs both Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) estimator with robust standard errors as its primary estimator and the and Augmented Mean Group (AMG) estimator with robust standard errors as a robustness test. The choice of these estimators is informed by their handling of the problem of cross-sectional dependence which can result in inconsistent and biased estimators and spurious significance in first generation panel data estimators such as the pooled ordinary least squares and fixed effects estimators.

The results of the CCEMG estimation, presented in table 6 and evaluated on the basis of the 5% level of significance, reveals that financial development has a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth in SSA, while financial openness, labor force and institutional quality measured as the rule of law have negative and statistically insignificant effects on economic growth among countries in the SSA countries included in the study. On the other hand, the result shows that government effectiveness has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in the SSA.

Table 6: Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) Estimates

lrgdp	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
fdin	0.250451	0.2218881	1.13	0.259	-0.18444 0.685344
fpen	-0.01089	0.0221598	-0.49	0.623	-0.05432 0.032541
lexce	0.022397	0.0375833	0.60	0.551	-0.05126 0.096059
lbor	-0.00955	0.0215192	-0.44	0.657	-0.05172 0.03263
goef	0.078319	0.0230065	3.40	0.001	0.033227 0.123411
rula	-0.00215	0.0329967	-0.07	0.948	-0.06683 0.062518
__00000M_lrgdp	1.038164	0.1189786	8.73	0.000	0.80497 1.271358
__00000L_fdin	-0.12836	0.8979318	-0.14	0.886	-1.88827 1.631555
__00000L_fpen	0.014207	0.0790213	0.18	0.857	-0.14067 0.169086
__00000L_lexce	-0.02399	0.0455962	-0.53	0.599	-0.11336 0.065373
__00000L_lbor	0.009023	0.021963	0.41	0.681	-0.03402 0.05207
__00000L_goef	-0.1281	0.1252508	-1.02	0.306	-0.37359 0.117383
__00000L_rula	-0.07189	0.0894011	-0.80	0.421	-0.24711 0.103332
_cons	-1.32037	3.163834	-0.42	0.676	-7.52138 4.880628
Root Mean Squared Error (sigma):		0.0307	Wald chi2(6)		16.8
			Prob > chi2		0.0101

Source: Authors` (2026).

The mean economic growth ($_00000M_lrgdp$) has a probability value of 0.000 which is highly significant. This confirms the existence of cross-sectional dependence (commonality of shocks) among the SSA countries included in the study. The probability value of the Wald test, 0.0013, indicates that the entire model is statistically significant, thus implying that the regressors are collectively responsible for variations in economic growth in SSA. Furthermore, the root mean-square error value of 0.0306 which provides information on the difference between the predictions of the model and the observed values is low, indicating that the model adequately fits the data on the variables.

To ensure the adequacy of the results derived by the study, the CCEMG estimates are subjected to further diagnostic testing on the basis of the Modified Wald Test for groupwise heteroskedasticity. The result of this test, presented in table 7, indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity. This means that there is heteroskedasticity among the countries included in panel. To address this issue, the model for the study is estimated through the use of the CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors.

Table 7: Modified Wald test for groupwise heteroskedasticity

H0: $\sigma(i)^2 = \sigma^2$ for all i	
chi2 (39)	3681.50
Prob > chi2	0.000

Source: Authors` (2026).

The result of the CCEMG with robust standard errors estimation of the study model, presented in table 8 also indicates that financial openness has a negative but statistically insignificant effects on economic growth in SSA, while the economic growth effect of financial development is positive

but statistically insignificant. The CCEMG with robust standard errors estimates also reveal that institutional quality measured as the index of government effectiveness and labor force have a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in the SSA countries included in the study sample.

Table 8: Common Correlated Effects Mean Group (CCEMG) Estimates with Robust Standard Errors

lrgdp	Coef.	Std.Err.	Z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
fdin	0.321902	0.20827	1.55	0.122	-0.0863	0.730104
fpen	-0.00121	0.001174	-1.03	0.302	-0.00351	0.00109
lexce	-0.0125	0.029131	-0.43	0.668	-0.0696	0.044594
lbor	-0.00463	0.003141	-1.47	0.14	-0.01079	0.001524
goef	0.054547	0.019346	2.82	0.005	0.016628	0.092465
rula	0.018582	0.016465	1.13	0.259	-0.01369	0.050851
__00000M_lrgdp	0.964642	0.079594	12.12	0.000	0.80864	1.120644
__00000L_fdin	-0.30745	0.926216	-0.33	0.74	-2.1228	1.507897
__00000L_fpen	-0.07017	0.044729	-1.57	0.117	-0.15784	0.017496
__00000L_lexce	0.015729	0.041747	0.38	0.706	-0.06609	0.097552
__00000L_lbor	-0.00423	0.011107	-0.38	0.703	-0.02592	0.01747
__00000L_goef	0.030312	0.083658	0.36	0.717	-0.13365	0.194278
__00000L_rula	-0.03019	0.064301	-0.47	0.639	-0.15621	0.095839
_cons	1.973588	2.203654	0.9	0.37	-2.3455	6.292671
Root Mean Squared Error (sigma):		0.0307	Wald chi2(6)		15.03	
			Prob > chi2		0.02	

Source: Authors` (2026).

On the other hand, in contrast to the CCEMG estimates, the CCEMG with robust standard errors estimates reveal that institutional quality measured as the index of the rule of law and the exchange rate have positive but statistically insignificant effects on economic growth in SSA. Furthermore, the mean economic growth (__00000M_lrgdp) also has a probability value of 0.000 which is highly significant, thus confirming the existence of cross-sectional dependence (commonality of shocks) among the countries in SSA. The probability value of the Wald test, 0.02, also indicates that the entire model is statistically significant. Again, the root mean-square error value of 0.0307 which provides information on the difference between the predictions of the model and the observed values is also low, indicating that the model adequately fits the data on the variables.

In order to test for the possibility of multicollinear relationships among the regressors included in the CCEMG estimates with robust standard errors, the estimated model is subjected to multicollinearity testing through the use of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test. The result of the VIF test, presented in table 9, indicates that regressors, while being moderately correlated are not multicollinear. This is because their respective VIF values are less than 5.

Table 9: Variance Inflation Factor Test for Multicollinearity

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
fdin	2.35	0.425601
goef	2.33	0.428779
rula	1.38	0.72387
lexce	1.38	0.724784
fpen	1.15	0.869613
lbor	1.06	0.946295
Mean	VIF	1.61

Source: Authors` (2026).

Finally, as a robustness test, the model for the study is re-estimated through the use of the Augmented Mean Group (AMG) estimator with robust standard errors. The result of this re-estimation, presented in table 10, reveals that financial development has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in SSA. This result is not in line with the results of the CCEMG estimators. In line with the CCEMG estimates with robust standard errors, the result also indicates that financial openness, exchange rate and labor force have negative but insignificant effects on economic growth in the countries included in the study, the effect of institutional quality measured as the index of the rule of law is positive but insignificant, while the effect of institutional quality measured as the index of government effectiveness is positive and significant.

The root mean-square error value of 0.0633 also low, indicating that the model adequately fits the data on the variables. The probability value of the Wald test, 0.0001, also indicates that the entire model is statistically significant.

Table 10: Augmented Mean Group (AMG) Estimator with Robust Standard Errors

lrgdp	Coef.	Std.Err.	Z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
fdin	0.579839	0.150683	3.85	0.000	0.284505 0.875172
fpen	-9.4E-05	0.00047	-0.2	0.842	-0.00102 0.000828
lexce	-0.01504	0.022984	-0.65	0.513	-0.06009 0.030008
lbor	-0.00592	0.004156	-1.43	0.154	-0.01407 0.002222
goef	0.084285	0.026016	3.24	0.001	0.033294 0.135276
rula	0.001672	0.026828	0.06	0.95	-0.05091 0.054254
__00000R_c	1.048613	0.066382	15.8	0.000	0.918507 1.178718
_cons	23.20229	0.484891	47.85	0.000	22.25192 24.15266
Root Mean Squared Error (sigma):			0.0633	Wald chi2(6)	27.81
				Prob > chi2	0.0001

Source: Authors` (2026).

However, this study adopts the results of CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors as its baseline and primary result. The choice of this result is anchored on its root mean square error value (0.0307) which is smaller than that of the AMG estimator with robust standard errors (0.0633), indicating a better goodness of fit due to its ability to filter out the noise due to the existence of cross-sectional dependence in among the cross-sectional unity in a stricter manner. It also implies that CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors better handles the earlier identified

problem of heteroskedasticity and, error structure than the AMG estimator with robust standard errors.

While the result of the AMG estimator with robust standard errors has more significant variables, such higher number of significant variables might be attributed to the way the two estimators address the issue of unobserved common factors. The statistical significance of the coefficient of financial development in the results of the AMG estimator with robust standard errors might be due to its being inflated by the unobserved common shocks which are better filtered by the CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors.

Furthermore, due to its mean group nature, the CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors, takes into account the differences in the responses of each SSA country in the panel to shocks by using cross-sectional averages, thus avoiding the “bias pitfall” associated with the assumption of uniformity in the response of all SSA countries to common shocks. The implication of this for the results is that the proportion of economic growth in SSA which is a product of external influences during the period covered by the study such as the Great Recession of 2007 to 2008, Ebola virus pandemic of 2014 to 2016 and Covid-19 pandemic of 2020 to 2023 are filtered out, with the significant regressor being interpreted as an intrinsic-leftover-effect once the common shocks have been removed. The regressors thus reflect the net effect rather than country specific effects.

Based on the forgoing, the results with respect to the growth effects of financial development as derived from the CCEMG estimation with robust standard errors, is not consistent with the findings made by the studies by Ibrahim and Alagidede (2018), Jibir et al. (2023), Fengju and Wubishet (2024) with respect to SSA and East Africa (EA). It is not also in line with the findings made with respect to Nigeria by studies by Shobande (2017), Ikubor et al. (2022) and Nuhu and Ima`il (2024). All of this study found financial development to have significant growth effects in SSA, EA and Nigeria. On the other hand, the result is in line with the findings made by the study by Dan`Asabe and Mustapha (2023) which indicated that financial development has a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The finding with respect to the economic growth effects of financial openness does not also conform to the findings made by the studies by Seti et al. (2025) and Liu et al. (2026).

The result with respect to the economic growth effects if financial openness and financial development implies that capital account liberalization as implemented by the governments in SSA countries and financial development policies introduced during the period, while having the potential to contribute to economic growth SSA, have not had the desired effect. This may be due to challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and insecurity which limit the effectiveness of financial development and openness as growth driving forces in the region.

The result with respect to the growth effects of the exchange rate indicates that any attempt at exchange rate devaluation with a view to boosting exports and economic growth in SSA will not lead to the desired growth effects. The insignificant effect of the exchange rate also implies that it is not a predictor of economic growth among the SSA countries included in the study. Furthermore, the negative relationship between institutional quality measured as the index of the rule of law and economic growth in SSA may be explained by the potential high cost of compliance for businesses with the rule of law in the region. It may also be due to the existence of large informal sector in the region which accounts for a significant proportion of economic activities and employment. In such a case, improvements in the rule of law will naturally be expected to

have negative effects on economic activities in the region. The insignificant effect of the index of the rule of law implies that it is not a predictor of economic growth among the SSA countries

On the other hand, the study found that institutional quality measured as government effectiveness had a positive and significant effect on economic growth in SSA. This result is particularly pertinent, given the characteristics of the CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors because it implies that government effectiveness is a key driver of sustainable economic growth in SSA, irrespective of the state of the global economy. This emphasizes the importance of a strong and effective government to growth of the economies of SSA, as well as the relevance of efforts geared towards improving their effectiveness by governments in the region. Finally, it should be noted that the mean group nature of the CCEMG estimator with robust standard errors implies that though institutional quality measured as the index of government effectiveness has a positive mean effect on economic growth in SSA, differences might exist in the specific growth response of each SSA country to improvements in government effectiveness.

3. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The governments of Sub-Saharan African countries have over the years implemented a wide range of measures targeted at financial openness and development with a view to attaining higher and sustained rates of economic growth. In light of this, this study investigated the effect of financial openness and financial development on economic growth in SSA. From the results, the study concludes that both financial openness and financial development have not had significant effects on economic growth in SSA during the period covered by the study. On the other hand, the study found that institutional quality measured as government effectiveness was a significant predictor of the growth of the economies of SSA during the period covered by the study. In particular, the results indicated that government effectiveness had a positive relationship between government effectiveness and economic growth in the region.

Based on the findings, the study recommends that the governments of the countries in SSA implement measures to address the challenges to the effective utilization of financial services in the region such as infrastructural deficits and financial literacy. SSA's Central Banks should also introduce measures targeted at encouraging lending to micro and small enterprises in the region, and encourage banks and other key institutions to improve channel their lending towards more employment generating-high economic priority sectors. Finally, the study recommends that efforts should be made towards improving the quality of government institutions with a view to increasing the effectiveness of government, through the implementation of reforms with respect to institutions such as the police and judiciary.

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